

Infected panicles after artificial inoculation with *Acrocyndrium oryzae* in Thailand.

Repl-ication	Infected panicles (%)		
	Spray suspension of spores	Injection suspension of spores	Check
1	80.9	78.1	0
2	73.3	69.7	0
3	72.4	77.8	0
4	65.9	77.3	0
Av.	73.1	75.7	0

The young panicles remained within the sheath, whose upper surface was entirely covered with dark-brown lesions.

We found that typical symptoms appeared after artificial inoculation by both spray and injection with a suspension of the fungus *Acrocyndrium oryzae* in the booting stage (see table). The experiment was conducted in nylon screen cages; insecticides were applied to eliminate mites or insects. The results indicate that the primary factor in rice abortion or sheath rot in Thailand is the fungus *Acrocyndrium oryzae*. The dispersion and severity of the disease may be related to the biological relationships between the sheath rot fungus and mites, the fungus and stem borers, or both. **W**

Research on the ecology and natural enemies of the rice stem borer *Diopsis thoracica* in Malawi

H. R. Feijen, University of Malawi, Present address: Universidade Eduardo Mondalane, Maputo, Mozambique

Diopsis thoracica flies spend the dry season in shady places along banks of streams, where they can be found in large swarms. In December, at the beginning of the rainy season, they move back to the rice fields. They lay eggs singly on rice stems or leaves, the highest numbers at about 25 days after transplanting. The larva enters the stem via the leaf sheath and develops there. The feeding larva causes yellowing of the terminal leaf (deadheart). Its occasional attack on older rice can cause whiteheads. Except when it attacks seedlings, the larva remains on the same stem until pupation; but just before pupation it may move to another stem or even another hill.

The eggs take an average of 3 days to hatch. The larval stage lasts approximately 38 days and the pupal stage 14 days. There is one main generation each rainy season and one partial second generation in later planted fields. In the dry season (Apr.–Nov.) the number of flies and the number of eggs laid in fields with a second crop are low.

Egg parasitoids seem to be the most important natural control against *D. thoracica*. Three species have been found: two species of the genus *Trichogramma*, which are presently being described; and *Trichogrammatoidea simmondsi*, which is less important. All 3 egg parasitoids were found to be susceptible to organophosphorous insecticides and chlorinated hydrocarbons. Application of phosphamidon in nurseries brought egg parasitism down to below 2%. Predation of eggs by small Carabid beetles and mites could reach 30%.

Up to 25% of the pupae were attacked by the parasitoid *Aprostocetus* sp. Adult flies were parasitized by six species of fungal pathogens. Crab spiders and Odonata were recorded as predators of the fly.

The effect of *D. thoracica* on transplanted rice is difficult to assess.

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Occurrence of the rice tarsonemid mite at IRRI

Kazushige Sogawa, visiting scientist, Entomology Department, International Rice Research Institute

A phytophagous tarsonemid mite was found infesting rice plants on the IRRI farm. The mite, identified as *Stenotarsonemus spinki* by Dr. Robert L. Smiley of the US Department of Agriculture, lives in colonies within the intercellular air space of the upper part of leaf sheaths and, occasionally, in the basal part of the midrib of leaf blades. It causes necrotic streaks in the interveinal epidermis (see photo).

When a female mite is artificially inoculated into the intercellular air space of a leaf sheath, it becomes gravid and, in 2 days, begins to lay eggs randomly at the rate of about 15/day over a period of 5 or more days. The eggs are opaque, ovoid, and large (125 × 80 microns) in comparison with the size of the adult. They hatch into 6-legged larvae in 2 to 4 days. The newly emerged larvae are opaque-white, about 140 microns long, and rather inactive. After feeding, they grow to about 300 microns long, and their wrinkled integument smoothens as the cuticle becomes tightly stretched. Then the larvae enter a quiescent stage.

The average duration of the active larval stage is 1 day and that of the quiescent stage, 2 days. The life cycle is

Necrotic streaks caused by the Tarsonemid mite on rice leaf sheaths.

completed in 6 days. The adults are slightly tanned, and about 245 microns long. The females at the preovipositional stage are far more active than the males, and are mainly responsible for dispersal. The males are often observed carrying quiescent larvae on their backs. The species is facultatively parthenogenetic; the virgin females lay only a few eggs, which produce only males. **W**

In one season approximately 10% of the seedlings were destroyed by larval attack. In the 1970–71 and 1971–72 seasons, when attacks were heaviest, even fields with almost 100% deadhearts recovered reasonably well. No significant differences in yield were found between sprayed and unsprayed fields. An attack by *Diopsis* larvae can have positive or negative effects on the growth of rice, depending on time and level of attack, general growing conditions, and rice variety. ❧

***Shirakiacris shirakii*, a new pest of paddy in Pakistan**

Mohammad Irshad, assistant entomologist, Pest Management Project, Agricultural Research Council, B-6, Al-Markaz, F-7/2, Islamabad, Pakistan

Several species of grasshoppers damage paddy in Pakistan but *Shirakiacris shirakii* was found for the first time. Its distribution is restricted to the hilly areas of Swat, Hazara, and had Kashmir, where the annual temperature is 17 to 18.5°C, annual precipitation is 950 to 1,730 mm, and elevation is 1,000 to 1,500 m. The pest is abundant in those areas. Adults are collected only from paddy, but nymphs are occasionally found on *Trifolium alexandrinum* and *Cynodon dactylon*. The insect remains associated with paddy throughout its life; nymphs feed on the leaves and adults feed on both leaves and grains. It seems to damage paddy considerably, especially in the earing stage when adults eat immature grains. The insect usually inhabits those fields where *Oxya multidentata* and *Hieroglyphus banian*, two other serious pests of paddy, are found. It feeds and develops on young maize and sorghum plants in the laboratory.

S. shirakii is a univoltine species. The eggs overwinter and hatch in May at about 24.5°C. Nymphs feed on rice nurseries and *C. dactylon*, and become adults in August or September. Oviposition begins a month later and continues until November. Several copulating pairs of *S. shirakii* have been seen on sunny November days in the harvested paddy fields, but on cloudy days they hide in

rice stubble or plant trash. Females are mostly gravid during this period and die after laying eggs. Neither adults nor nymphs could be collected from December to April; they cannot tolerate the severe cold winter. Egg pods are laid before winter – usually in the fields, preferably in sandy soil but seldom on levees. Each egg pod is buried in the soil at a depth of 2.5 to 5 cm and contains 24 to 45 eggs, averaging 39. The eggs are deep brown in color, and the froth plug is dirty brown.

The incubation period at 31 °C ranges from 17 to 23 days, averaging 20 days. Six instars of nymphal development are completed in 86 to 103 days (av. of 92 days), at about 23°C and 77% relative humidity. ❧

Outbreak of rice hispa in Nellore district, Andhra Pradesh, India

Venkata Rao G., junior plant pathologist, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Regional Rice Research Station, Nellore; and Muralidharan K., research unit-forecasting, Central Rice Research Institute, Regional Rice Research Station, Nellore 524003, India

Dicladyspa armigera, commonly known as rice hispa, is a major rice pest. Until recently, it had not been observed in the southern districts, but a severe outbreak was noted at the Regional Rice Research Station farm and many other parts of Nellore during the late kharif season, 1975–76. The main crop in Nellore – the locally evolved variety Bulk H9 (Molagolukulu) – was heavily infested.

The pest appears to have migrated from the northern districts from mid-November 1975 to the end of January 1976, after heavy rains in late October and early November 1975. After the rains, the prevailing high humidity and intermittent bright sunshine seem to have favored hispa development in epidemic proportions. The maximum temperature during the day never exceeded 29°C, and the minimum ranged between 17 and 20°C until the end of January 1976. Toward the end of January, a decline in the beetle population occurred synchronously with the rise in temperatures and the lowering of the relative humidity. Hispa exhibited a

Entries in the International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON) and the National Screening Nursery (NSN) with less than 1% of the leaf area damaged by rice hispa. Andhra Pradesh, India.

IRON	
IR2053-375-1-1-5	RD5
IR2058-74-2-1-1	Chianung-Sen 11
IR2063-152-3-2	B 452b-290-2-1-3
IR2063-185-2-2	Pelita 1-2
IR2068-65-3	C 168-134
Purple check 15/ IRI 103-1	IR2153-26-3-5-6 Bahagia (R check)
IR2070-178-2-3	IR1545-339-2-2
IR2070-210-3-3-4	IR2070-199-3-6-6
IR2070-288-2-2-5	IR22 (S check)
IR2070-614-6-4	IR5491-4-80 (Gihl)
IR2070-796-1-4-3	RPW 6-2
IR2070-834-1-2	IR20
BW 196	IR2153-15-1-10-3
BKN 6323-17	IR2031-114-2-3-1
BKN 6819-33-3-2-1-3	IR2153-26-3-5-2
BKN 6819-33-3-2-2-3	M1 48
BKN 6820-4-1-3	IET 1444
BKN 6820-6-3-2	
NSN	
RP 633-382-1-1-5-7	R 19-1-1-1
RP 974-97-8-1	R 45-1-2-2
R 8-2-4-1	R 49-2-2-2-1-1-1
R 8-12-1-1	

marked preference for younger plants.

Damage was also observed on many entries from the International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON) and the National Screening Nursery (NSN) trials, which were exposed to the large hispa population (see table). The severity of the epidemic is clear: more than 25% of the leaf area was lost in half of the IRON entries and in 95% of the NSN entries. Eight sprays were used consecutively from early November, almost at weekly intervals: Ambithion, Folithion, Sumithion, Sumithion with BHC, Sumithion with Endrin, and three sprays of Sevin with BHC. They were, however, effective only for 2 or 3 days. After that period, the hispa population rose to the original level, probably because of invasions of fresh insects from adjacent fields where no control measures were undertaken.

Various spray schedules were followed on the blast-susceptible variety BCP 1 to evaluate the effects of Phosvel 34% EC (*O*. 2,5 Dichloro-4 bromopheny 1) *O*-methyl phenylphosphonothionate) on blast. Although hispa severely damaged